

Ecotourism and Economic Development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to examine ecotourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was carried out based on the variable of this study. The survey research design was considered useful for the study. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 232 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A twenty-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Ecotourism and Economic Development of Calabar Municipal Questionnaire (EEDCMQ) was the instrument used for gathering data for the study. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools were used for data analysis. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between ecotourism and the economic development in the study area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the state government should ensure investment in basic infrastructure such as roads, better airports facilities and good transport system.

Keyword: Ecotourism, tourism, Calabar Municipal, Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Tourism has always been regarded as a means of economic modernization but has not been seriously considered as a means of social and cultural modernization, the concept of socioeconomic modernization emphasize improvement in various indicators, including improvement in living conditions and the quality of life and wellbeing of the population. Ezenagu (2013) posited that tourism is the sector with the biggest employer of labour in Nigeria as it is generating employment for millions of people and its effect rubs on every aspect of people from taxi drivers to Bank managers (Tunde, 2012) in 2002 the tourism industry generated an estimated 199 million jobs - one in every 13 jobs worldwide. Nigeria as at 2011, the Travel and Tourism industry was forecast to directly generate a total of 897, 500 jobs in 2012, and that happens to comprises of 1.4 % of total employment in Nigeria. Tourism generates finance for infrastructure development and generally increases citizen's welfare. It has also influenced the Nigerian aviation industry with the coming in of capital flights associated with oversea trip and an expansion of the same industry which had Nigerian Airways for a monopoly between the periods of 1985 to 1992. The increase is to the effect that as from 1992 there had been an influx of over 25 different carriers in the country. Tourist upon visitation, patronize local folk art such as straw baskets, hats, wooden carvings, ornaments, trinket and help improve the living standards of host areas (Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam & Oham, 2023). Tourism comes with a multiplier effect that rubs on other sectors of Nigeria's economy, namely: financial institutions, hospitals, transport, agriculture, environment and aviation (Ezenagu, 2013). Tourism is the main foreign exchange earner and the main source of job creation in the country. And so, income and prices are generally linked to the variables of demand for tourism.

Ecotourism is the management of tourism and conservation of nature in a way so as to maintain a fine balance between the requirements of tourism and ecology on the one hand and the needs of local communities for new job skills, income generating employment and better status for women. Ecotourism has become a need for everyone who wants to refresh from the routine fast city life. Ecotourism provides many interesting tours to the heart of Mother Nature. Ecotourism focuses on socially responsible travel, personal growth and environmental sustainability. Ecotourism typically involves travel to destinations where flora, fauna and cultural heritage are the primary attractions. Ecotourism is intended to offer tourists an insight into the impact of human beings on the environment and to foster a greater appreciation of our natural habitats (Kumar, 2007).

Calabar Municipal has the potentials to become one of the leading tourist destinations due to her rich cultural heritage, tourism sites, cuisines, attractions etc. and traces of the different types of tourism being found in it, has stimulated the development of a variety of allied infrastructure and facilities such as Calabar International Convention Centre (CICC), National Museum, Calabar, sport stadium, airport and more. Owing all the above listed tourism locations and facilities, one wonders if tourism contributes to the economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River state. Tourism is the number one employer of labor in the world and jobs created by tourism spreads across the economy in areas of construction, telecommunications, retail and manufacturing, thus, creating jobs in large number for young people, women, and minorities whether in small or medium size companies (Akpan & Obang, 2012).

The Malthusian theory was propounded by Thomas Robert Malthus in the year 1798. Malthus contends that the process of economic development is not automatic. Rather conscious, deliberate efforts are needed to bring it about. For instance, Malthus explains that mere increase in population cannot by itself lead to economic development unless there is increase in effective demand. He rejects Say's Law which says supply creates its own demand and that savings are automatically invested and constitutes a demand for capital goods. Malthus' important contribution shows that savings in the sense of not consuming is a mere negative act and instead of creating more demand it will lead to a decline in effective demand. Only savings which are furnished by increased gains and are invested create an effective demand. Thus, according to him, abstinence on the part of capitalists, far from accelerating economic growth, will in itself retard it. Hence, Malthus brings out an important fact expand that in advanced economy consumption, saving and investment all should simultaneously. Malthus attaches great importance to the accumulation of capital for economic development. He regards capital as indispensable to development. According to him, no permanent and continued increase of wealth can take place without a continued increase of capital. Besides, Malthus underlined the importance of foreign trade for speeding up economic development. Foreign trade provides incentives for investing, since it leads to the extension of the market for the goods produced and for greater division of labour resulting in increased output.

Tourism also helps economic activities to grow in a given country. Most people go into other countries for business tourism and they invest in such countries. The more tourists are found in a country, the more economic activities that take place. The population of foreign people in a country who depend on the country's resources can enhance economic development. There is another important fact brought out by Malthusian analysis of economic growth, namely, the structured

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change that takes place in the process of economic development i.e., a decline in the relative importance of agriculture as the economy moves forward. We know that economic development in developing countries is regarded as synonymous with the development of industries. Malthus' contribution to economic growth contains several elements that are relevant to the developing economies. His emphasis on production and distribution, capital accumulation and the creation of congenial non-economic factors is as valid today as was in his time.

The implication of the theory to this study is that, tourism increases the number of people in a given state. Most of these tourists have high demand for local resources. When local resources are highly demanded, demand becomes effective. Effective demand increases economic development and also increases investment opportunities. As tourists are attracted to tourist destinations, they contribute to increase in population of such destination and hence raise the effective demand of goods and services in such areas. The producers of such goods and services demanded by tourists in a bid to maximize profit will demand for more labour to increase in supply and this consequently leads to employment generation.

Ecotourism is a form of tourism which embraces tourism in the biophysical environment in natural areas. It is also a travel to natural areas, conserving the environment and improving the wellbeing of the local people. It incorporates ecologically sustainable activities, conservation supporting measures and involvement of local communities. Ecotourism is the management of tourism and conservation of nature in a way so as to maintain a fine balance between the requirements of tourism and ecology on the one hand and the needs of local communities for new job skills, income generating employment and better status for women. Ecotourism has become a need for everyone who wants to refresh from the routine fast city life. Ecotourism provides many interesting tours to the heart of Mother Nature. Ecotourism focuses on socially responsible travel, personal growth and environmental sustainability. Ecotourism typically involves travel to destinations where flora, fauna and cultural heritage are the primary attractions. Ecotourism is intended to offer tourists an insight into the impact of human beings on the environment and to foster a greater appreciation of our natural habitats. Ecotourism is an amalgamation of two separate concepts; ecology and tourism, but viewed jointly. The coinage assumes great significance both for ecological conservation and development of tourism. Tourism is now becoming a major socioeconomic activity, which contributes to the country and its economy. He also points out Nigeria potentials to develop as a major tourism attraction in the country (Kreg, 2010). Kreg (2010) in his paper titled ecotourism and other services derived from forests in the Asia-Pacific region made an attempt to prove that the growth rate for ecotourism will be higher than tourism generally. Tourism makes a substantial contribution to the region's economy.

Ecotourism in region and global has grown faster than tourism generally, and this probably will continue over the next several years. Ecotourism can capture biodiversity values and provide incentives for conservation and integrated conservation and development project include an ecotourism component. One is that ecotourism business can achieve financial viability (Kreg, 2010). Sangpikul (2017) conducted a study titled ecotourism impacts on the economy, society and environment of Thailand. The study examined how ecotourism tour operators and their guided tours contribute to the development of economic, social and environmental dimensions at ecotourism sites and local communities. Data for the study were collected from ecotourism tour operators through the interview and observation methods, and the contents were analyzed in accordance with ecotourism concepts and principles. The study revealed that the practices of tour operators and their guided tours contributed economic, social, and environmental benefits to the ecotourism destinations and local communities. Interestingly, the study found that the length (duration) and types of guided tours had different contributions and impacts on the three dimensions of sustainability. In particular, guided tours with a local visit contribute greater economic and social benefits to the local areas than tours without a local visit. Taylor, Hardner and Stewart (2009) similarly conducted a study aimed at examining Ecotourism and economic growth in the Galapagos. The study was an island economy-wide analysis. The study revisited and updated a 1999 economy-wide analysis predicting that increases in tourism would result in rapid economic as well as demographic growth on the Galapagos Islands. The study findings indicated that total income (that is, the gross domestic product) of the Galapagos increased by an estimated 78 per cent between 1999 and 2005, making the Galapagos economy among the fastest growing in the world.

Tourism continued to be far and away the major driver of economic growth. Nevertheless, population growth via new migration to the islands nearly erased the effect of economic growth on per-capita household income. These findings raise questions about the compatibility of ecotourism and conservation in this unique ecological setting. Gumede and Nzama (2019) also conducted a research on ecotourism as a mechanism for local economic development: the case of communities adjacent to the Oriibi Gorge Nature Reserve, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. The study was conducted at the Oriibi Gorge Nature Reserve and surrounding communities (Murchison and Eshobeni). The population of the study comprised of the municipal officials, community tourism organization, Oriibi Gorge Nature Reserves Management, community leaders, and households of the communities adjacent to the Oriibi Gorge Nature Reserve. A sample of 384 respondents was drawn from the population using

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a convenience sampling technique. Exploratory mixed methods design was adopted by the study, which suggests that both qualitative and quantitative modes of research enquiry were used during the collection, analysis and interpretation of data. Survey questionnaires were used to collect the data through face-to-face mode of enquiry. Qualitative data were analyzed through content analysis, while quantitative data were analyzed through Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version. 24). The findings of the study demonstrate that ecotourism contributes to the local economic development of the study area through employment creation and capacity building.

The study of Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam and Oham (2023) investigated medical tourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was carried out based on the variable of this study. The survey research design was considered useful for the study. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 232 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A twenty-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Medical Tourism and Economic Development Questionnaire (MTEDQ) was the instruments used for gathering data for the study. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools was used for data analysis. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between religious tourism and the economic development in the study area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the State government should ensure investment in basic infrastructure such as roads, better airports facilities and good transport system. Rajasenan, Manaloor and Abraham (2012) in a study sought to examine the socio-economic aspects of sustainable ecotourism development in Kerala. Data for the study was obtained from a primary survey by dividing the ecotourism destinations in Kerala into three zones, 230 from south zone, 220 from central zone and 200 from north zone with a total sample size of 650 based on the notion of community-based ecotourism initiatives of the state. The result of the study confirms that ecotourism has helped to enhance the livelihood of the marginalized community. With well-knit policies it is possible to tag ecotourism of Kerala as an important tourism destination in the global tourism map.

The literature reviewed indicates a great potential of the various types of tourism reviewed to the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State and Nigeria as a whole. It comes with economic benefits to host destinations, including increased income, taxes, employment, and economic diversification and regeneration. This is to be achieved through the appraisal of the tourism resources of the nation and the combination of both natural and human capacities to transform the industry into a job creating and foreign exchange earner that will meet the economic wellbeing of the nation at large. Tourism, as an economic activity, is being used to help support bolster an economy and regional development.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to assess how ecotourism relate to economic development in Calabar Municipal.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide this study;

There is no significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the survey research design. It involves the collection of data to accurately and objectively describe existing phenomena. This design is employed because the study intends to gather information ready existing among the population under study. Moreover, adopting the survey helps the researcher to gather required data from the sampled respondents and generalize it to a large population. The area adopted for this study is Calabar Municipal of Cross River State. Calabar Municipal lies between latitude 04° 57' 06"North of the equator and longitude 08° 19' 30"East of the Greenwich Meridian. In the North, the Municipal is bounded by Odukpiani Local Government Area in the North-East by the great Kwa River. Its Southern shores are bounded by the Calabar River and Calabar South Local Government Area. It has an area of 33 1.551 square kilometres. It also has ten wards. Two ethnic groups form the indigenous population. These are the Quas and the Efiks. However, because of its cosmopolitan status, there abound people from all parts of the state and Nigeria in the city. Calabar Municipal Government Area plays a dual role. Apart from being the capital city of Cross River State, it also plays its role as headquarters of the southern senatorial district. By virtue of its location along the water front, the Efiks embraced western culture. They carried on successful trade with early Europeans. Fishing is another occupation identified with them. The Quas on the other hand occupy the bulk of the hinterland of Calabar where farmers, hunters, traders and blacksmiths are found. Calabar Municipal climate can be described generally as tropical within the equatorial hot-wet climate of southern

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Nigeria which is characterized by heavy amount of rainfall because of the south west wind that blows from Atlantic Ocean. Two seasons dominate the area; the wet and dry seasons. The wet season commences from late April, peaks in July/August and declines gradually till December/January.

The study area is endowed with many tourist sites/attractions such as National museum, Hope Waddel Training Institute, U.J Esuene Sport Stadium, West African People Institute (WAPI), Nigeria Port Authority (NPA), Export Processing Zone (EPZ), Pandrillus (Drill Ranch), CERCOPAN, Calabar International Convention Centre (CICC), Tinapa Business Resort, Millennium Park/cenotaph, Garment Factory and Peace Park etc. The targeted populations for this research are adults living in Calabar Municipal of Cross River State. The researcher considered males and females above the ages of 18 years to participate in the research because of their ability to understand and their knowledge of current trends. Calabar Municipal has a total population of 371,022 people from 2019 population estimates.

The sampling procedure adopted for this study is the simple random sampling technique (SRST). Simple random sampling technique is a means by which researchers give members of his or her population equal and independent opportunity of being selected. The simple random sampling technique was used to select ten (10) streets from Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. This was done using the hat and draw method. Here, the names of the streets were written on papers and folded in paper balls and put in a container. The researcher blindly picked one ball at a time until the 10 streets for the research was completed. In selecting the respondents that would be used for the study, the proportional simple random sampling technique will be adopted to select 0.5% of respondents in each of the selected streets. Finally, the researcher will adopt the accidental sampling technique to administer her questionnaire to the respondents in the selected communities. Only those willing to participate in the study will be given the opportunity to do so. These techniques will be adopted to avoid possible bias. The sample of this study comprise of 242 respondents selected from 10 streets in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. They consist of both male and female residents in the sampled streets.

The instrument employed for data collection was a questionnaire titled, Ecotourism and Economic Development of Calabar Municipal Questionnaire (EEDCMQ) designed by the researcher with the help of the supervisor. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A was design to collect the respondent's demographic data such as sex and age, while section B comprises twenty (20) items designed to measure tourism and economic development of Calabar Municipal. The questionnaire was the main instrument used for data collection. The data used for this research was sourced from primary sources, The Primary data were gathered through the respondents from face to face administration of questionnaires. This is because questionnaire can be more easily quantified and analysed. The construction of the questionnaire succumbs to the rule of simplicity, clarity, precision and relevant so as to elicit the quantitative data it seek. The questionnaire contained close ended questions to aid the respondent in minimize the risk of misinterpretation and allow them to understand the question carefully in order to give the correct response the questionnaire administered. After collecting the questionnaire, scores will be assigned to each item according to the sections. The four likert scale will be employed in this study. The scale is as follows; Strongly Agree (SA) = 4; Agree = 3; Disagree (D) = 2; Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	117	50.4
Female	115	49.6
Total	232	100.0

The above Table 1 show that 117 respondents out of the 232-population sampled were male constituting 50.4% while 115 respondents were female which constitutes 49.6% making it a total of 100%.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
18-29	68	29.3
30-39	92	39.7
40-49	40	17.2
50 and above	32	13.8
Total	232	100.0

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The percentage distribution table above shows that, 68 respondents out of the sampled were between the ages of 18-29 years constitution 39.3%, 92 respondents were between the age range of 30-39 years making 39.7% of the sampled population. 40 respondents fall between the ages of 40-49 which constitutes 17.2% while 32 respondents were within the age range of 13.8 and above representing 13.8% of the total population.

Hypothesis Testing

There is significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal LGA of Cross River State.

This hypothesis was tested using Pearson product moment correlation analysis. This is because, the independent and dependent variables were both measured continuously. The result of the analysis is as presented in table 3.

Table 3: Result of Pearson product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar municipal local government.

Variables	N	X	S.D	r-value	Sig.
Ecotourism	232	16.55	1.757	.233**	.010
Economic development	232	15.11	1.363		

**correlation is significant at .01 level, df=230, critical r=.158.

The result presented in table 3 shows the correlation between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. It revealed a calculated r-value of .233 which is statistically greater than the critical r-value or .158 at .01 level of significance with 230 degrees of freedom. As a result of this, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was upheld. The implication of this is that ecotourism has a significant effect on economic development in Calabar municipal local government area of cross river state.

Discussion of Findings

The hypothesis states that ecotourism has no significant effect on economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State. This hypothesis was however rejected on the ground that the calculated r-value of .233 was found to be significantly greater than the critical r-value of .158. The implication of this result is that ecotourism has significant effect on economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State. The findings of this study is in tandem with a study by Sangpikul (2017) whose study on ecotourism pacts on the economy, society and environment of Thailand found a significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development. The study is also in agreement with a similar study by Taylor et al. (2009) who examined ecotourism and economic growth in the Galapagos. The study found ecotourism to be a major driver of economic growth. Gumedede and Nzama (2019) study on ecotourism as a mechanism for local economic development also agrees with the findings of the present study as it found that ecotourism contributes to the local economic development of the study area through employment creation and capacity building.

Conclusion

Following the results that emerged from the analysis of data collected for this study, the following conclusions were made: There is significant relationship between ecotourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion made thereof, the State Government should ensure investment in basic infrastructure such as roads, better airports facilities and good transport system.

References

Akpan, E. I. & Obang, C. E. (2012). Tourism: A Strategy for Sustainable Economic Development in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3 (2), 12-22.

Ecotourism and Economic Development ... (Usang et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://ddoi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10114350>

- Bodger, D. H., Bodger, P. M. and Frost, H. (2004). Educational travel: Where does it lead? School of Continuing Education, University of Nottingham.
- Ceballos-Lascuráin., H. (1996) Tourism, ecotourism and protected areas: The state of nature-based tourism around the world and guidelines for its development, Cambridge: IUCN Publications.
- Chew, A. and Croy, W.C. (2011). International Education Exchanges: Exploratory Case Study of Australian-Based Tertiary Students' Incentives and Barriers. *J. Teach. Travel Tour*, 71,253-270.
- Ezenagu, N. (2013). Tourism a viable path for wealth creation in Nigeria: An analysis of Awka Metropolis. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 2(9). 2319-7064.
- Ezenagu, N. (2013). Tourism a viable path for wealth creation in Nigeria: An analysis of Awka Metropolis. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 2(9). 2319-7064.
- Gumede, T.K. and Nzama, A.T. (2019). Comprehensive participatory approach as a mechanism for community participation in ecotourism. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 8(4), 1-11.
- Kreg, L. (2010). Policies for maximizing nature tourism's eco-logical and economic benefits. New York: World Resources Institute.
- Onnoghen U. N., Unimtiang U. S., Ogban O. N., Ogbaji D. I., Iyam S. O. & Oham S. B., (2023). Medical tourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria.
- Patterson, I. (2006). Growing older. Tourism and leisure behaviour of older adults. Oxfordshire, UK, CABI.
- Rajasenan, D., Manaloor, V., and Abraham, B. (2012). Tourist Profiles and Characteristics vis-à-vis Market Segmentation of Ecotourism Destinations in Kerala. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 3, 134-144.
- Rajasenan, D., Manaloor, V., and Abraham, B. (2012). Tourist Profiles and Characteristics vis-à-vis Market Segmentation of Ecotourism Destinations in Kerala. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 3, 134-144.
- Sangpikul, A. (2017). Ecotourism Impacts on the Economy, Society and Environment of Thailand. *Journal of Reviews on Global Economics, Life science Global*, 6, 302-3 12.
- Sayre, S. and King, C. (2010). Entertainment and Society" Influences, Impacts and Innovations. New York, Routledge.
- Tunde, M. (2012). Harnessing tourism potentials for sustainable development: A case of Owu water falls in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 14, 3-22.